

Gelatine-assisted Defect Engineering in LaCoO₃ and its Impact on Oxygen Electrocatalysis

Lalita Sharma^[a], Mariana Klementova^[b], Kateřina Minhová Macounová^[a], Petr Krtil^{*[a]}

^[a]J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Dolejškova 3, Libeň, 18223
Praha 8, Czech Republic

^[b]Institute of Physics of the CAS, v.v.i., Na Slovance 2, 182 21 Prague, Czech Republic

Supporting information

Fig S1: Rietveld refinement of lanthanum cobalt oxide synthesized in presence of 7.5 g/L gelatin assuming Cobalt oxide and lanthanum oxides as impurities as indicated in picture inset. The figure of merit of the refinement is mentioned in table S1.

Table S1: Parameters of full Rietveld refinement of the diffraction patterns of lanthanum cobalt oxide perovskites synthesized with variable amount of gelatin.

	LaCoO ₃	ESD	Co (II, III) oxide	ESD	La ₂ O ₃	ESD	R _{wp} , R _{exp} , χ^2 , GOF
0 g/L	0.9924	0.0029	0.0076	0.0029	-	-	R _{wp} = 3.74 %, R _{exp} = 3.54 %, χ^2 = 1.12, GOF = 1.06
0.3 g/L	0.9976	0.0018	0.0024	0.0018	-	-	R _{wp} = 2.43 %, R _{exp} = 1.34 %, χ^2 = 3.29, GOF = 1.81
0.8 g/L	0.9968	0.0030	0.0032	0.0030	-	-	R _{wp} = 2.85%, R _{exp} = 1.25%, χ^2 = 5.20, GOF = 2.28
1.5 g/L	0.9959	0.0021	0.0017	0.0018	0.0024	0.0011	R _{wp} = 2.66%, R _{exp} = 1.31%, χ^2 = 4.12, GOF = 2.03
2.5 g/L	0.9730	0.0027	0.0158	0.0021	0.0112	0.0016	R _{wp} = 2.96 %, R _{exp} = 1.19%, χ^2 = 6.19, GOF = 2.49
5.0 g/L	0.9576	0.0059	0.0261	0.0051	0.0163	0.0029	R _{wp} = 4.59%, R _{exp} = 4.33%, χ^2 = 1.12, GOF = 1.06
7.5 g/L	0.9487	0.0040	0.0070	0.0024	0.0245 LaCO 0.0198	0.0018 0.0026	R _{wp} = 3.52%, R _{exp} = 1.29%, χ^2 = 7.45, GOF = 2.73

Fig. S2: FESEM micrographs of lanthanum cobalt oxide synthesized by varying amount of gelatin concentration in solution mixture.

Fig. S3: Particle size distribution of LaCoO_3 synthesized with varying gelatine amount in the range between 0.0 g/L to 7.5 g/L. The corresponding average particle sizes are given in the Figure legend.

Figure S4 HRTEM micrographs of samples prepared with gelatine concentration of 0.0g/L (top row), 1.5 g/L(middle row), and 7.5 g/Lwith the corresponding FFT in the inset.

Figure S5: TEM micrographs and displacement distribution calculated by geometrical phase analysis (GPA) of samples prepared with gelatine concentration of 0.0 g/L (top row), 1.5g/L (middle row), and 7.5 g/L. (column 1) TEM images with the yellow arrows pointing towards nanoparticles of secondary phases (Co_3O_4 and La_2O_3), (column 2) HRTEM images along $[100]$ pseudocubic / $[1-11]$ rhombohedral direction, (column 3) FFT displaying superstructure reflections at $1/3$ and $2/3$ of the reciprocal unit cell highlighted by yellow arrows, (column 4) X component of displacement, and (column 5) Y component of displacement.

Figure S6: TEM micrographs and electron diffractions of samples prepared with gelatine concentration of 0.0 g/L (top row), 1.5 g/L (middle row), and 7.5 g/L. (column 1) low magnification TEM images, (column 2) TEM images with the yellow arrows pointing towards nanoparticles of secondary phases (Co_3O_4 and La_2O_3), (column 3) electron diffraction patterns and (column 4) interpretation of electron diffraction (green– LaCoO_3 , blue– Co_3O_4 , magenta– La_2O_3).

Figure S7: TEM observations of Co_3O_4 nanoparticles in sample prepared with gelatine concentration of 7.5 g/L. (Top row) TEM and HRTEM images with 4.7\AA corresponding to (111) d-spacing of Co_3O_4 , (middle row) electron diffraction pattern and its interpretation (green— LaCoO_3 , blue— Co_3O_4 , magenta— La_2O_3), (bottom row) elemental composition by EDX showing elemental maps and representative spectra of area 1 showing LaCoO_3 and area 2 showing Co_3O_4 .